

Design and multiscale simulation of Wool/PLA biocomposites: Experimental validation and impact failure analysis

Zbigniew Stempień^{a,*}, Marcin Barburski^a, Justyna Pinkos^a, Nawar Kadi^b

^a Institute of Architecture of Textiles, Faculty of Material Technologies and Textile Design, Lodz University of Technology, Żeromskiego 116, 90-924 Łódź, Poland

^b Department of Textile Technology, The Swedish School of Textiles, University of Borås, Högskolan i Borås S-501 90 Borås, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Wool/PLA biocomposites
Impact strength
FEM
LS-DYNA

ABSTRACT

This study presents numerical and experimental investigations of wool fiber-reinforced polylactide (PLA) biocomposites. In the first stage, a MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 (LS-DYNA) material model was developed based on mechanical tests performed on samples with two fiber-to-PLA mass ratios: W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40. In the second stage, the models were applied in Charpy impact simulations to evaluate impact strength and identify dominant failure mechanisms. The results show that fiber content, orientation, and impact direction strongly influence energy absorption and failure behavior. Samples impacted along the fiber direction exhibited significantly higher strength and stiffness compared to transverse loading. Increasing PLA content enhanced stiffness and load-bearing capacity but led to more brittle failure. The W40/PLA60 composite absorbed the highest energy but failed abruptly, while W60/PLA40 exhibited a more gradual damage progression and distributed deformation of the composite structure. Microscopic analysis confirmed these differences, with fiber pull-out dominating in axial impacts and matrix cracking and delamination in transverse ones. The developed simulation model captures these behaviors and supports the structural design of wool/PLA composites, offering a basis for future predictive modeling of sustainable biocomposites.

1. Introduction

Both climate change and its related environmental policies are accelerating the search for new materials with lower carbon footprints and increased biodegradability [1]. Consequently, there has been an increased interest in recent years that offers a potential substitute for traditional composites reinforced with synthetic fibers for specific structural uses. These environmentally friendly composites are generally made of natural matrices and reinforced with plant or animal fibers. Biodegradable matrix materials such as gelatin, chitosan, polybutylene succinate (PBS), polylactide (PLA), and many others have been investigated. Of these, PLA stands out especially because it possesses good mechanical characteristics, is biocompatible, and can be produced from renewable resources like corn starch, sugarcane, potato starch, and sugar beet [2,3]. PLA is extensively used in thermoformed food packaging [3], in technical textiles that are biodegradable [4], surgical sutures, implants, drug delivery systems [3], and in structural members with low strength requirements. Even though it has many advantages, PLA's brittleness and low resistance to impact makes the material's application under dynamic loading conditions severely limited. It has

been reported that the Charpy impact strength of PLA is approximately 19 kJ/m^2 [5]. Due to the inherent brittleness of PLA, it cannot be used in a larger scope as a structural material and requires additional reinforcement. To keep the structure's biodegradability, reinforcements are made using primary plant-based [6–9] natural fibers. However, research is also being conducted on reinforcing PLA matrix biocomposites with natural fibers of animal origin, such as wool fibers [10,11] and natural silk [12–14]. Experimental studies show that such PLA composites can achieve even better mechanical properties, thermal insulation, and fire resistance compared to PLA composites reinforced with plant-based fibers. Wool fibers, due to their wavy structure, in contrast to the linear structure of natural silk, are particularly considered for reinforcing PLA composites intended to operate under dynamic loading conditions [11]. Although specific commercial applications for wool/PLA composites are still limited, their biodegradability and energy-absorbing potential make them suitable for future use in acoustic panels, packaging, or interior components in automotive applications, similar to other natural fiber-reinforced PLA materials [15,16]. In terms of mechanical properties, it has been shown that wool/PLA composites achieved a 46 % higher tensile strength and a 13 % higher modulus of elasticity compared to

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zbigniew.stempien@p.lodz.pl (Z. Stempień).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.115066>

Received 6 August 2025; Received in revised form 30 September 2025; Accepted 31 October 2025

Available online 2 November 2025

0264-1275/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

pure PLA, indicating effective structural reinforcement [11]. Furthermore, impact strength tests demonstrated a significantly higher energy absorption capacity for wool/PLA composites compared to pure PLA, suggesting that reinforcing the composite with wool fibers effectively enhances the dissipation of energy generated under dynamic loading [11].

Biocomposites intended for use as structural materials operating under dynamic loading conditions must possess appropriate mechanical strength and impact resistance. Existing numerical and experimental studies indicate that the dominant damage mechanisms of PLA biocomposites under dynamic loading are primarily fiber pull-out and breakage, matrix cracking, and delamination [17,18]. An effective tool for evaluating damage mechanisms, structural deformation, and assessing local stresses and strains under dynamic loading is numerical modeling using the finite element method (FEM) [17,19–21]. The most widely used FEM solver for simulating composite structures subjected to various types of impact is LS-DYNA [19]. However, it should be noted that the validation of numerical models against experimental data is essential to ensure their predictive accuracy [17,20,21]. The literature describes various approaches to modeling composites, including macro- and micromechanical models, which are most often implemented in FEM preprocessors [19]. The few FEM studies on PLA matrix composites reinforced with natural fibers show significant mechanical nonlinearity and a strong dependence on strain rate [21]. This contrasts with composites based on epoxy matrices reinforced with carbon or glass fibers, which can generally be modeled as linear-elastic up to the point of failure [19]. Despite extensive experimental research on the impact resistance of biocomposites, numerical models are still at an early stage of development, and a key issue remains the formulation of appropriate material models for biocomposites.

Taking the above issues into account, the aim of this study was, in the first stage, to develop a material model MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 (LS-DYNA) for wool/PLA composites based on experimental strength tests of actual composite samples prepared in two material variants. In the second stage, using the developed material models, simulation studies of Charpy hammer impact on the composite samples were conducted to determine the impact strength and to identify the dominant damage mechanisms in the composites. In the final, third stage, the numerical model was validated by comparing the impact strength of the composites determined from numerical simulations with the results of experimental tests. The novelty of this work lies in the fact that wool/PLA biocomposites have not previously been parametrized and validated in LS-DYNA using the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 progressive-damage model. Unlike previous studies focused mainly on fabrication or quasi-static performance, this work integrates multiscale experimental characterization, dynamic Charpy impact testing, numerical simulation, and microscopic validation of failure mechanisms, providing a transferable parameterization framework for other natural fiber-based biocomposites.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Wool/PLA composites intended for further research were manufactured in four stages. Commercially available PLA fibers (6.7 dtex, 60 mm; Trevira GmbH, Germany) and coarse wool fibers with an average diameter of $33 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ and length of $88 \pm 15 \text{ mm}$ were used to manufacture needle-punched nonwoven preforms. No chemical treatment of wool fibers was applied prior to composite fabrication.

2.2. Fabrication of wool/PLA composites

The composites were produced in two variants differing in the mass ratio of wool fibers to PLA, i.e., 40%/60% (denoted as W40/PLA60) and 60%/40% (denoted as W60/PLA40) following the scheme

presented in Fig. 1.

In the first stage, wool and PLA fibers in the desired ratio were processed using a laboratory-scale modified Laroche opener to loosen and soften the fibers for improved blending. The resulting fiber blend was then carded using a laboratory-scale carding machine to align the fibers predominantly in the machine direction, promote intermixing, and remove residual impurities. In the second stage, five nonwoven layers with preferential fiber orientation along the machine direction were prepared and stacked without altering the fiber orientation. This multilayer assembly was then consolidated into a cohesive mat using needle punching (HUNTER Fiberlocker Lab Needle Punch, 11" width) with a constant stitch density of 70 stitches/cm². In the third stage, two such needle-punched mats were stacked again with the same fiber orientation and thermally bonded into a single composite plate using a hot press at 190 °C for 7 min under a pressure of 2 MPa. The resulting composite was placed between two steel cooling plates to ensure uniform cooling and dimensional stabilization. Photographs of the fabricated composite plates (W60/PLA40 and W40/PLA60) after the complete processing sequence are shown in Fig. 2.

2.3. Mechanical testing for material model calibration

Specimens for mechanical and impact testing were laser-cut from the composite plates in both the direction aligned with the fiber orientation

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the wool/PLA composite fabrication process.

Fig. 2. Photographs of the fabricated wool/PLA composite plates used in mechanical testing: W60/PLA40 (left) and W40/PLA60 (right). Labels and surface markings were added for internal identification during the experimental campaign.

and the perpendicular direction. Prior to testing, the cut samples were conditioned at 23 °C and 50 % relative humidity to improve the repeatability of the results. Tensile, compression, and shear tests were conducted to determine the parameters for the material model MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55. Table S1 presents the required parameters for this material model and the methods used to determine them [22]. The elastic moduli E_1 (EA) and E_2 (EB), as well as the Poisson's ratio ν_{21} (PRBA), for both composite variants were determined based on tensile tests (EN ISO 527–4) conducted in the axial and transverse directions, at a strain rate of 2 mm/min. These tests also provided values for the tensile strengths XT and YT, as well as the ultimate strains in the axial (DFAILT) and transverse (DFAILM) directions. Shear properties were determined through tests aimed at identifying both the shear moduli and the shear strengths. The in-plane shear modulus G_{12} (GAB) was determined using the V-notched rail shear test (ASTM D7078), which allows for precise characterization of shear behavior in high-stiffness laminates. Additionally, using the same standard, tests were conducted to determine the through-thickness shear moduli G_{31} (GCA) and G_{32} (GCB), which describe the shear properties across the thickness of the composite (through the laminate layers). The Poisson's ratios ν_{31} (PRCA) and ν_{32} (PRCB), which describe the through-thickness deformations in relation to the axial and transverse directions, were estimated based on the approach outlined in [23].

$$\nu_{31} = \frac{E_3}{E_1} \cdot \nu_{21} \text{ oraz } \nu_{32} = \frac{E_3}{E_2} \cdot \nu_{21} \quad (1)$$

The compressive strength of the composite in the axial and transverse directions was determined through compression testing (EN ISO 14126), from which the through-thickness elastic modulus E_3 (EC), compressive strengths XC and YC, and the ultimate compressive strain DFAILC were obtained. The normal failure stress (NFLS) was determined based on a tensile test perpendicular to the laminate layers, following ASTM D7291. This test allowed for the identification of the maximum stress at which failure occurs in the direction normal to the composite. The shear failure stress (SFLS) was determined using the V-notched rail shear test (ASTM D7078), defined as the maximum shear strength in the through-thickness direction of the composite.

2.4. Charpy impact testing

The resistance of composites to dynamic loading was assessed using Charpy impact testing according to EN ISO 179–1, performed with a Zwick D-7900 impact hammer (Zwick, Germany) with an impact energy of 4 J. Based on these tests, the Charpy impact strength of the composites (a_{CU}) was analyzed using equation (2), and the dominant failure mechanisms were identified, such as delamination, matrix cracking, and

fiber pull-out.

$$a_{CU} = \frac{E}{A} \quad (2)$$

In equation (2), E represents the energy absorbed by the specimen during impact, and A is the cross-sectional area at the impact point (i.e., specimen thickness \times height). The obtained Charpy impact strength values were used to validate the material model MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55, which was adopted as the material model for the wool/PLA composites in the Charpy impact simulations. For this purpose, the Charpy impact strength results obtained from the simulations were compared with the experimental results.

2.5. Numerical modeling (LS-DYNA)

The numerical modeling of the Charpy hammer impact on the wool/PLA composite specimens was carried out in LS-DYNA, replicating the actual experimental conditions of the Charpy tests, including the specimen geometry, support conditions, and impact parameters (Fig. 3).

The geometric model of the composite specimen was developed as a two-layer system, in accordance with the actual structure of the composite, with external dimensions of 80 \times 10 \times 2 mm, which comply with the standard requirements for Charpy impact testing. A numerical mesh was then generated for this geometry using HEXA/SOLID elements with dimensions of 0.2 \times 0.2 \times 0.2 mm. These element sizes were selected based on mesh convergence analysis, which examined the influence of decreasing element size on the amount of energy absorbed by the specimen during Charpy hammer impact. It was found that further mesh refinement had no significant effect on the absorbed kinetic energy values. The supports, corresponding to the actual supports in the Charpy testing machine, were modeled as rigid, fixed objects. The distance between the supports was 62 mm. The Charpy hammer was modeled as a solid body, including the striking head, pendulum arm, and hinge. A numerical mesh for the supports and the impact hammer was created using TETRA/SOLID elements with a 0.25 mm size at the impact point, with gradual size increase in areas not in contact with the specimen. The simulation was initiated from the moment the hammer head contacted the specimen. The initial velocity of the hammer was 2.9 m/s, corresponding to a kinetic energy of 4 J with a hammer mass of 0.95 kg. The model did not include additional damping at the hinge, and the pendulum movement was free after impact, allowing for a realistic representation of experimental conditions. A rigid material model (MAT_RIGID) was applied to both the supports and the Charpy hammer. In the simulations, the material model for the specimen was based on MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 (Table S1), which accounts for orthotropic mechanical properties and progressive damage mechanisms

Fig. 3. Finite element model of the Charpy impact test setup used for simulating the dynamic response of the composite specimen.

characteristic of composites, such as matrix cracking and delamination. The parameters for this model were derived from strength tests conducted on the developed wool/PLA composites. The contact conditions between the Charpy hammer and the supports with the specimen were modeled using the AUTOMATIC_SURFACE_TO_SURFACE contact formulation, incorporating both static and dynamic friction coefficients set at 0.2. This model allowed for precise representation of dynamic interactions, ensuring realistic contact and frictional forces between the hammer head and the composite. To model the interface between the two layers in the wool/PLA composite, the AUTOMATIC_SURFACE_TO_SURFACE_TIEBREAK contact was used with OPTION = 6, which enables progressive layer separation based on local normal failure (NFLS) and shear failure (SFLS) stresses, experimentally determined from tensile and interlaminar shear tests. Additionally, contact damping

with SOFT = 1 was applied in this formulation to minimize abrupt force fluctuations and improve numerical stability.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Mechanical characterization of wool/PLA composites

Fig. 4a presents the stress–strain curves obtained from tensile tests conducted in the axial and transverse directions for the wool/PLA composites. The W40/PLA60 composite variant exhibited higher tensile strength and a greater Young’s modulus in both directions compared to the W60/PLA40 variant. In the axial direction, the W40/PLA60 composite reached a maximum stress of approximately 53 MPa at a failure strain of ca. 0.14. In the transverse direction, the maximum stress was lower, around 38 MPa, confirming the anisotropic nature of the material. This behavior results from the fiber orientation within the composite structure, which predominantly supports loads in the axial direction. The data obtained from these tests were used to determine the material model parameters EA, EB, PRBA, XT, YT, DFAILT, and DFAILM for the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 model (Table 1). Fig. 4b shows the results of shear tests conducted in three material planes: AB

Table 1

Experimentally determined mechanical properties of wool/PLA composites used in the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 material model.

MAT_54/55 parameter	Parameter unit	Composite type W40/PLA60	W60/PLA40
RO	kg/m ³	989.5 ± 6.4	823.3 ± 5.8
EA	MPa	564 ± 23.2	534 ± 18.7
EB	MPa	410 ± 16.3	389 ± 14.8
EC	MPa	177 ± 12.5	141 ± 7.9
PRBA	–	0.27	0.27
PRCA	–	0.085	0.072
PRCB	–	0.116	0.098
GAB	MPa	241 ± 41.0	218 ± 26.7
GBC	MPa	47 ± 5.2	37.0 ± 4.4
GCA	MPa	56.4 ± 4.7	40.6 ± 3.8
DFAILT	–	0.14 ± 0.027	0.13 ± 0.024
DFAILC	–	–0.12 ± 0.022	–0.11 ± 0.019
DFAILM	–	0.13 ± 0.025	0.12 ± 0.018
DFAILS	–	0.12 ± 0.018	0.09 ± 0.015
XT	MPa	53.3 ± 7.4	38.4 ± 4.8
XC	MPa	50.1 ± 4.9	37.7 ± 3.4
YT	MPa	31.8 ± 2.7	26.5 ± 2.5
YC	MPa	42.2 ± 3.2	30.1 ± 3.7
SC	MPa	9.5 ± 0.36	7.3 ± 0.44
SFLS	MPa	1.9 ± 0.31	1.6 ± 0.28
NFLS	MPa	1.8 ± 0.22	1.5 ± 0.18

Fig. 4. Stress–strain curves for wool/PLA composites: a) tensile tests in axial and transverse directions, b) shear tests in AB, AC, and BC planes.

(in-plane) and AC and BC (through-thickness). The highest shear strength was recorded in the AB plane, attributed to the presence of fibers that reinforce shear resistance in this orientation. In the AC and BC planes, where shear occurs between composite layers, the recorded stresses were significantly lower, which is typical for layered materials. The W40/PLA60 composite exhibited better mechanical properties in all planes compared to W60/PLA40, with the most pronounced difference observed in the AB plane. The improved mechanical performance of the W40/PLA60 composite was likely due to more effective fiber embedding in the matrix, facilitating better load transfer at the fiber–matrix interface. Based on these tests, the shear moduli G_{AB}, G_{AC}, and G_{BC}, as well as the strength parameters SC, SFLS, and DFAILS, were determined and incorporated into the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 material model (Table 1).

Fig. 5a shows the stress–strain curves obtained from compression tests conducted in the axial and transverse directions for the wool/PLA composites. In all cases, the W40/PLA60 composite variant exhibited higher stiffness and greater compressive strength compared to the W60/PLA40 variant. In the axial direction, the maximum stresses were approximately 50 MPa for W40/PLA60 and 38 MPa for W60/PLA40, with comparable ultimate strains of ca. 0.01. In the transverse direction, the maximum stress values were lower – about 42 MPa for W40/PLA60 and 30 MPa for W60/PLA40 – highlighting the anisotropic nature of the material resulting from the directional fiber alignment. The improved performance in the axial direction is attributed to the dominant orientation of the wool fibers, which effectively reinforce the composite in that direction. The data obtained from these tests were used to determine the material model parameters X_C, Y_C, and DFAILC for the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 model (Table 1). Fig. 5b presents the results of compression tests performed in the direction perpendicular to the composite layers (through-thickness direction). In both composite variants, W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40, significantly lower elastic moduli were observed compared to the in-plane directions. The calculated elastic moduli E_C were 177 MPa for W40/PLA60 and 141 MPa for W60/PLA40. This behavior is typical for layered materials, in which the polymer matrix, PLA in this case, plays a dominant role in the through-thickness direction. The results were used to define the E_C parameter in the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 material model (Table 1).

Fig. 6 shows the stress–strain curves for the wool/PLA composites obtained during tensile strength tests conducted perpendicular to the composite plane. For both composite variants, W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40, the curves exhibit an almost linear behavior up to the point of reaching the maximum stress, after which a gradual decline is observed due to structural failure and loss of load-bearing capacity. As seen in Fig. 6, the maximum stress for the W40/PLA60 variant was

Fig. 6. Through-thickness tensile stress–strain curves for wool/PLA composites used to determine the normal failure stress (NFLS).

approximately 1.8 MPa, while for the W60/PLA40 variant it was around 1.6 MPa. The obtained maximum stress values were assigned to the NFLS parameter in the material model MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 (Table 1).

3.2. Charpy impact response of wool/PLA composites

Fig. 7 shows the results of Charpy impact tests of wool/PLA composites in the axial and transverse directions, obtained on the Charpy test stand. The results clearly show, that the composite manufactured in the W40/PLA60 variant exhibits higher Charpy impact strength in both directions compared to the W60/PLA40 variant. During the impact of the hammer in the axial direction of the composite, the impact strength values were about 29 kJ/m² for W40/PLA60 and 21 kJ/m² for W60/PLA40, and during the impact in the transverse direction of the composite, about 23 kJ/m² and 17 kJ/m². Obtaining higher Charpy impact strength for the W40/PLA60 composite in both directions compared to the W60/PLA40 composite can be attributed to the higher PLA content, which likely resulted in better filling of the inter-fiber spaces. This, in turn, contributed to a more continuous and uniform matrix structure, enhancing fiber–matrix adhesion and reducing internal defects. The improved structural integrity of the matrix phase enables more effective stress transfer and energy dissipation under impact loading, despite the

Fig. 5. Stress–strain curves for compression tests of wool/PLA composites: a) axial and transverse directions, b) through-thickness direction. The curves represent two material configurations with different wool/PLA weight ratios: 40/60 and 60/40.

Fig. 7. Charpy impact strength of wool/PLA composites in axial and transverse directions.

inherently brittle nature of PLA. It should be noted that the Charpy test measures the amount of the hammer’s kinetic energy absorbed by the sample. In the tests performed, the measured values of this energy were 0.48 J and 0.36 J for the W40/PLA60 composite and 0.38 J and 0.29 J for the W60/PLA40 composite in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. The demonstrated differences in both the amount of absorbed energy and the Charpy impact strength depending on the impact direction confirm the anisotropic structure of the material, which results from the unidirectional orientation of the fibers in the composite layers.

3.3. Microscopic evaluation of damage mechanisms

To identify the dominant damage mechanisms in the tested composites resulting from Charpy impact, a macroscopic analysis of the fracture surfaces and side walls of the damaged samples was carried out using an optical microscope (Figs. 8–9). The analysis was conducted for both fiber orientation directions. After Charpy impact testing, microscopic observations of the W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40 composite samples revealed significant differences in damage mechanisms. These differences are primarily attributed to the varying wool-to-PLA content in the composites and the orientation of the fibers relative to the impact direction (Figs. 8–9). For the W40/PLA60 composite, pronounced delamination between layers was observed in the side view (Fig. 8a), especially in samples subjected to transverse impact, where the delamination extended over a much greater distance compared to samples impacted in the axial direction, where it was confined to the area immediately surrounding the impact zone. In the frontal view (Fig. 8b), a broad whitening zone was visible, indicating localized plasticization and cracking of the PLA matrix, evidence of intense deformation within this phase of the material. The fracture surface images clearly illustrate the dominant damage mechanisms. A fiber pull-out effect was observed in the axial direction (Fig. 8c), indicating that friction between the fibers and the matrix played a key role in absorbing impact energy. In contrast, in the transverse direction (Fig. 8d), the damage was dominated by brittle cracking of the matrix, with little or no evidence of fiber pull-out. This suggests that the fibers contributed minimally to load transfer in this orientation.

In the case of the W60/PLA40 composite (Fig. 9), the damage pattern is different. In the side view (Fig. 9a), under axial impact, tearing of the outer layer was observed, while the layer on the impact side of the Charpy hammer remained cracked but structurally continuous. A slight delamination between the layers in the fracture zone of the composite can also be seen. For the transverse direction, both layers did not rupture

Fig. 8. Microscopic images of the W40/PLA60 composite after Charpy impact test: a) Side view of the fractured sample, b) Front view of the impacted surface, c) Close-up of the axial fracture surface, d) Close-up of the transverse fracture surface.

Fig. 9. Microscopic images of the W60/PLA40 composite after Charpy impact test: a) Side view of the fractured sample, b) Front view of the impacted surface, c) Close-up of the axial fracture surface, d) Close-up of the transverse fracture surface.

but only developed cracks, suggesting a different material behavior, more flexible and less prone to delamination initiation. In the frontal view (Fig. 9b), the whitening zone is significantly smaller compared to W40/PLA60, which may result from the lower PLA content, and thus a smaller contribution of this phase to plasticization and impact energy absorption. The close-up of the fracture surface in the axial direction (Fig. 9c) shows a partially torn layer, while in the transverse direction (Fig. 9d), the layer remains largely intact. The observed differences may be attributed to the more flexible nature of the W60/PLA40 composite, resulting from the lower content of the stiff and brittle PLA matrix. This configuration may promote more elastic-plastic deformation of the sample, especially under bending between supports, thereby limiting the initiation and propagation of cracks. In a structure with lower PLA content, stresses may be more effectively dissipated within the spatial arrangement of the fibers, despite their limited role in transverse load transfer. As a result, the W60/PLA40 composite, despite its lower stiffness and mechanical strength, shows reduced tendency for complete layer disintegration under impact.

Although carding was applied to align fibers along the machine direction, the subsequent needle punching process introduced local fiber entanglement and partial misalignment (Figs. 8c–d and 9c–d). This is a known effect of barbed needles penetrating the fiber mat, and it results in a composite structure with a predominantly axial orientation but locally disordered fiber arrangement [24].

3.4. Numerical simulation of Charpy impact (LS-DYNA)

To analyze the phenomena occurring during impact loading of wool/PLA composites, numerical simulations of Charpy hammer impact were conducted using LS-DYNA software. The numerical model replicated the actual geometry of the Charpy hammer and the tested specimens, as well as boundary conditions corresponding to the physical test. The simulations included two composite variants (W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40)

and two fiber orientation directions relative to the impact direction – axial and transverse. The analysis aimed to compare the dynamic response of the composites under impact conditions and to identify the main damage mechanisms depending on the material configuration. For this purpose, the time evolution of von Mises stress distribution and four damage variables (DMV) generated by the LS-DYNA solver for the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 material model were analyzed. The simulations enabled the evaluation of damage localization and progression over time, and their comparison with experimental results served as a basis for further validation of the numerical model.

3.4.1. Stress distribution and deformation

Fig. 10 presents the evolution of von Mises stress and deformation of the composite during Charpy hammer impact for two material variants, W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40, and two impact directions. The simulation stages are shown at 1 ms intervals, allowing observation of the progressive deformation of the specimen and the stress distribution along its length. For the W40/PLA60 composite in the axial direction (Fig. 10a), stress initially concentrates in the outer layers of the specimen and then propagates into the inner layers. A distinct zone of high stress intensity is visible, leading to complete fracture of the specimen approximately 5 ms after the impact. In the transverse direction (Fig. 10b), strong localized stresses are also observed, but their intensity is lower, indicating a different failure mechanism, primarily matrix cracking and delamination. For the W60/PLA40 composite, a more uniform stress distribution is observed in both the axial (Fig. 10c) and transverse (Fig. 10d) directions, with maximum stress values clearly lower than in the W40/PLA60 variant. The specimen exhibits significant bending between the supports, but no complete layer fracture occurs, as was the case with the W40/PLA60 composite. The stress distribution and smaller concentration zones indicate a more continuous and elastic deformation behavior, which is also confirmed by the lack of full layer rupture in the microscopic images (Fig. 9). The von Mises stress

Fig. 10. Evolution of von Mises stress and specimen deformation during Charpy impact simulation for wool/PLA composites: a) W40/PLA60 – axial impact, b) W40/PLA60 – transverse impact, c) W60/PLA40 – axial impact, d) W60/PLA40 – transverse impact. Time steps are shown every 1 ms.

distribution over time reflects the actual differences between the analyzed composites. The variant with higher PLA content (W40/PLA60) is characterized by greater stiffness and a more brittle response, leading to faster damage localization and propagation. In contrast, the W60/PLA40 composite, due to its greater flexibility, does not undergo complete disintegration.

3.4.2. Damage evolution (DMV variables)

To analyze the damage mechanisms in wool/PLA composites subjected to Charpy impact loading, four damage variables (DMVs) generated by the LS-DYNA solver for the MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 material model were examined. The selected variables included: DMV1 – damage under tensile loading along the fibers, DMV2 – damage under compressive loading along the fibers, DMV3 – damage under transverse tensile loading, and DMV4 – damage under transverse compressive loading. Each variable ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 represents complete material failure and 1 indicates an undamaged state. Analyzing these variables allowed for tracking the initiation, propagation, and localization of damage over time. Figs. S1–S4 show the spatial distribution of each variable as color maps at different time points, highlighting key stages such as the onset of damage, its peak development, and the initial loss of the composite's load-bearing capacity. For the W40/PLA60 composites, the analysis of the DMV1 and DMV2 variable distributions reveals differences in the timing of damage initiation and its subsequent development, resulting from the combined action of compressive and tensile stresses (Fig. S1). Fiber damage under compression (DMV2) begins earlier, around 2.67 ms, in the hammer–specimen contact zone, which corresponds to the stress concentration on the impact side. In contrast, tensile damage (DMV1) initiates later, at around 4.2 ms, on the opposite side of the specimen where maximum tensile stresses typical of three-point bending occur. The peak intensity of damage is observed at 4.5 ms for DMV1 and at 4.45 ms for DMV2. At these moments, the damage variables reach values close to 0, indicating nearly complete fiber failure in the critical material zones. The distribution of these variables clearly shows the location of the most heavily loaded areas and the point at which the material can no longer sustain additional load increases. Structural load-bearing failure, understood as the point at

which the material loses its ability to effectively transfer forces, occurs around 5.15 ms, corresponding to the drop in hammer contact force in the simulation. Although specimen deformation can still progress after this time (through further arm displacement and deformation after structural failure), DMV values close to 0 indicate that the material in the analyzed zones is already fully degraded. The fully damaged zones (with DMV close to 0) interrupt the continuity of the composite, directly leading to the loss of its mechanical integrity. These observations are consistent with the experimental results (Fig. 8c), where the dominant damage mechanisms were fiber pull-out and matrix plasticization in the axial direction. The agreement between simulation and experimental results confirms the validity of the applied LS-DYNA model and its suitability for analyzing the behavior of wool/PLA composites under impact conditions.

Fig. S2 presents the distribution of damage variables DMV1 and DMV2 in the W60/PLA40 composite subjected to Charpy hammer impact in the axial direction. Damage under compression (DMV2) initiates in the contact zone between the hammer and the composite, where compressive stress concentrations are highest. Tensile damage (DMV1), on the other hand, appears on the opposite side of the sample due to critical tensile stresses induced by bending. Compression damage (DMV2) begins at approximately 2.26 ms, with the region of maximum damage observed around 2.79 ms. Tensile damage (DMV1) initiates at around 2.74 ms and peaks near 2.8 ms. The distribution of these variables indicates that, in the W60/PLA40 composite, the damaged areas are less extensive compared to the W40/PLA60 variant. This suggests a more localized failure pattern and a higher degree of structural flexibility. Regions where DMV values approach 0 are concentrated in the lower layer of the specimen (on the tensile side), while the upper layer shows noticeable compressive damage without full delamination. Structural load-bearing capacity is lost at approximately 6.6 ms, corresponding to a further drop in contact force observed in the simulation. Compared to the W40/PLA60 variant, the W60/PLA40 composite exhibits lower tensile damage intensity, likely due to its reduced stiffness and greater capacity for localized bending without the formation of extensive cracks. The lower PLA content reduces the composite's susceptibility to brittle failure, enabling more effective stress dissipation

within the fibrous network. The localized nature of damage observed in the simulation is also confirmed by microscopic analysis (Fig. 9c), where only one layer of the composite is visibly torn in the axial direction, without the extensive delamination seen in the W40/PLA60 variant.

Fig. S3 presents the damage variables DMV3 and DMV4 for the W40/PLA60 composite subjected to Charpy hammer impact in the transverse direction relative to fiber orientation. In this configuration, tensile damage (DMV3) initiates at approximately 4.1 ms, while compressive damage (DMV4) appears significantly later, around 5.47 ms. This difference in the timing of damage initiation is attributed to the dominant role of the PLA matrix in the transverse direction. Since the fibers in this orientation do not effectively carry the load, tensile stresses more readily lead to material failure. The maximum damage intensity is observed at 5.75 ms for DMV3 and 5.68 ms for DMV4, with variable values locally reaching nearly 0, indicating complete material degradation in the affected zones. The damage distribution is more extensive than in the axial direction, especially for DMV3, suggesting a greater susceptibility of the composite to transverse tensile failure. Structural load-bearing capacity is lost around 6.5 ms, which coincides with the end of energy absorption by the specimen. Although deformation may continue beyond this point, the regions where DMV3 and DMV4 approach 0 represent zones of complete failure, disrupting material continuity and leading to structural collapse. These damage patterns align well with experimental observations (Fig. 8d), where brittle matrix cracking dominated in the transverse direction, with no visible signs of fiber pull-out.

Fig. S4 presents the distribution of damage variables DMV3 and DMV4 in the W60/PLA40 composite subjected to Charpy hammer impact in the transverse direction relative to fiber orientation. Tensile damage (DMV3) initiates at approximately 2.74 ms, while compressive damage (DMV4) appears slightly earlier, around 2.26 ms. Peak damage values are recorded at 2.8 ms for DMV3 and 2.79 ms for DMV4. The damage distribution reveals a more limited extent and lower intensity compared to the W40/PLA60 composite (Fig. S3), indicating a more dispersed deformation pattern and a reduced tendency for crack propagation. Load-bearing capacity is lost around 7.6 ms, coinciding with the point in the numerical analysis where no further increase in absorbed energy is observed. In this composite variant, loaded transversely, DMV3 and DMV4 reach values close to 0 only in small, localized regions, without the formation of large-scale damage zones. This result is consistent with microscopic observations (Fig. 9d), where no complete layer rupture was noted in the transverse direction – only local cracking without significant signs of delamination. The limited whitening and absence of distinct delaminated zones suggest minimal plasticization of the PLA matrix, in line with the simulation results, which show a lack of

broad regions with $DMV \approx 0$. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the lower PLA content in the W60/PLA40 composite enhances its ability to undergo elastic–plastic deformation in the transverse direction, effectively limiting crack initiation and propagation. Compared to the W40/PLA60 variant, W60/PLA40 exhibits a lower tendency toward interlayer failure and delamination, resulting in a different and more cohesive failure pattern under impact loading.

3.4.3. Force–displacement and absorbed energy curves

Fig. 11 presents a comparison of the response of wool/PLA composites under Charpy hammer impact, shown as force–displacement curves (Fig. 11a) and energy–time curves (Fig. 11b) obtained from numerical simulations. Clear differences are visible in the shape of the curves depending on the composite variant and the direction of hammer impact relative to fiber orientation. These differences reflect the influence of wool and PLA content, as well as fiber orientation, on the composite's dynamic response. For the W40/PLA60 composite in the axial direction, the highest force value was observed ca. 55 N at a hammer displacement of 8.9 mm from the point of contact with the specimen. In the transverse direction, the maximum force was 34 N, corresponding to a hammer displacement of approximately 10.3 mm. The W60/PLA40 composite generally exhibited lower hammer interaction forces compared to W40/PLA60. The maximum force values were approximately 38 N at 7 mm displacement and 25 N at 10 mm displacement in the axial and transverse directions, respectively. The W40/PLA60 composite, due to its higher content of the stiff and brittle PLA matrix relative to wool fibers, is characterized by lower deformability but higher peak force. In contrast, the W60/PLA40 composite, which contains more fibers and less matrix material, shows lower stiffness and greater susceptibility to elastic–plastic deformation, resulting in lower peak force values. A characteristic feature of the force–displacement curves is their two-phase progression in all analyzed cases. The initial rise in force is almost linear, corresponding to the elastic response of the composite. This is followed by a distinct plateau or drop in the curve, indicating the onset of local damage, such as matrix plasticization, initial fiber breakage, or interlayer delamination. After this phase, the force increases again up to a maximum value, after which a sharp or gradual drop is observed, depending on the composite variant and the direction of impact relative to fiber orientation. The W40/PLA60 composite in the axial direction is characterized by a sudden drop in force, indicating rapid failure, while the other configurations show a more gradual decline, suggesting a more distributed damage pattern. These observations are consistent with the distributions of the DMV variables and the microscopic analysis, particularly the intense fiber pull-out in W40/PLA60 axial (Fig. 8c) and the limited damage in W60/

Fig. 11. Simulated response of wool/PLA composites under Charpy impact: a) force–displacement curves, b) absorbed energy–time curves. Results are shown for W40/PLA60 and W60/PLA40 configurations in both axial and transverse directions.

PLA40 transverse (Fig. 9d). The energy–time curves (Fig. 11b) support these conclusions. The W40/PLA60 composite in the axial direction absorbs energy rapidly, reaching a final value of approximately 0.44 J. For the same material in the transverse direction, the energy absorbed is 0.34 J. The W60/PLA40 composite absorbs less energy, 0.36 J in the axial direction and 0.32 J in the transverse direction, with the energy increase being more gradual and extended over time. This behavior indicates a greater capacity for elastic–plastic deformation without sudden failure.

3.4.4. Comparison between experiments and simulations

Table 2 presents a comparison of the Charpy impact strength results for the tested wool/PLA composite variants, depending on the hammer impact direction relative to the fiber orientation, calculated based on both experimental tests and numerical simulations. For each variant, the relative difference between the values obtained from the two approaches is also shown. In these tests, the highest Charpy impact strength was obtained for the W40/PLA60 composite in the axial direction, with values of 28.9 kJ/m² and 22.3 kJ/m² from experimental and numerical studies, respectively. In the transverse direction, the obtained Charpy impact strength values were lower, 20.8 kJ/m² experimentally and 17.0 kJ/m² numerically. The differences depending on the fiber orientation are due to the favorable alignment of the fibers relative to the load direction and the higher PLA content in the W40/PLA60 composite, which translates to greater stiffness and a better ability to transfer forces. In contrast, when the hammer impacts in the transverse direction, the fibers contribute minimally to load transfer, and the loads are carried mainly by the PLA matrix, which has lower resistance to cracking. For the W60/PLA40 composite, lower Charpy impact strength values were obtained in both directions. For axial impact, the Charpy impact strength values were 23.4 kJ/m² and 17.9 kJ/m² from experimental and numerical tests, respectively, which can be attributed to the more flexible nature of the material resulting from the lower PLA content and higher wool fiber content. In the transverse direction, the lowest impact strength values were recorded, at 17.1 kJ/m² experimentally and 16.0 kJ/m² numerically. In this case, the deformation and failure were more dispersed, and the impact strength obtained from the numerical simulation closely matched the value measured in the experimental tests.

It should be noted that the Charpy impact strength values obtained from the simulations were lower than those obtained from the experimental tests. The relative differences between the experimental and numerical values ranged from 6.5 % to 23.5 %. These deviations can be considered typical for modeling fiber-reinforced composite materials with natural fibers, which are characterized by high structural variability, challenges in accurately representing interfacial adhesion, and geometric simplifications in the numerical model. What is most important, however, is that the simulations accurately reflect the trends observed in the experimental tests, both in terms of absolute impact strength values and the differences between composite variants and hammer impact directions. This confirms the suitability of the applied model for analyzing impact behavior and optimizing wool/PLA composites.

4. Conclusions

Based on experimental tests of tensile, compressive, and shear strength for two variants of wool/PLA composites, material models (MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55) were developed by determining all the required parameters. The conducted numerical simulations using these models, along with experimental tests and microscopic observations, enabled a comprehensive evaluation of the Charpy impact strength of wool/PLA composites under Charpy hammer impact with an energy of 4 J. The results clearly demonstrate that the fiber-to-PLA mass ratio, fiber orientation, and hammer impact direction relative to the fiber alignment have a significant influence on the damage processes,

Table 2

Comparison of Charpy impact strength obtained experimentally and through LS-DYNA simulations for different wool/PLA composite configurations.

Configuration	Impact direction	Impact strength (experiment), kJ/m ²	Impact strength (simulation), kJ/m ²	Difference, %
W40/PLA60	Axial	28.9	22.3	22.9
W40/PLA60	Transverse	20.8	17.0	18.3
W60/PLA40	Axial	23.4	17.9	23.5
W60/PLA40	Transverse	17.1	16.0	6.5

energy absorption, and overall Charpy impact strength. In general, composite samples loaded in the direction aligned with the fiber orientation exhibited significantly higher impact strength and stiffness compared to those loaded in the transverse direction. Furthermore, increasing the PLA content while decreasing the wool fiber content led to greater stiffness and load-bearing capacity, but also resulted in a more brittle failure behavior. The W40/PLA60 composite achieved the highest force and energy absorption values but failed abruptly, whereas the W60/PLA40 composite showed a more continuous, plastic deformation profile and a more dispersed damage pattern. Microscopic analyses confirmed the differences in damage mechanisms – fiber pull-out dominated in axial configurations, while brittle matrix cracking and delamination were observed in the transverse direction. The validation of the LS-DYNA numerical model using the developed MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE_54/55 material model, by comparing experimentally and numerically determined Charpy impact strength values, demonstrated satisfactory agreement. The differences between experimental and simulation results ranged from 6.5 % to 23.5 %, which is considered acceptable for fiber-reinforced composites with natural fibers. The simulations accurately predicted the location and development of damage, as well as the course of the force–displacement and energy–time curves. Tracking the damage progression in short time intervals provides valuable insight into the dominant failure mechanisms and supports future optimization of wool/PLA composites under dynamic loading. The developed material model represents the key contribution of this work and can be applied in other finite element simulations involving wool/PLA composites.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zbigniew Stempien: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marcin Barburski:** Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Justyna Pinkos:** Software, Investigation. **Nawar Kadi:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marcin Barburski reports financial support was provided by European Union. The other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The research conducted by the authors was carried out as part of the project “Sustainable Industrial Design of Textile Structures for Composites”, which is funded by the European Union. Grant Agreement no. 101079009 Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03/Twinning. Acronym: SustDesignTex.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.115066>.

Data availability

All data supporting the findings of this study are included in the article and **Supplementary Information**. Additional datasets are available from the corresponding author upon request.

References

- [1] E. Hertwich, R. Lifset, S. Pauliuk, N. Heeren, Resource Efficiency and climate Change: Material Efficiency strategies for a Low-Carbon Future, A report of the International Resource Panel, United Nations Environment Programme, Nairobi, Kenya, 2020.
- [2] M. Jamshidian, E.A. Tehrani, M. Imran, M. Jacquot, S. Desobry, Poly-Lactic Acid: production, applications, nanocomposites, and release studies, *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 9 (5) (2010) 552–571.
- [3] P.S. Ferreira, S.M. Ribeiro, R. Pontes, J. Nunes, Production methods and applications of bioactive polylactic acid: a review, *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 22 (4) (2024) 1831–1859.
- [4] A. Jabbar, M. Tausif, H.R. Tahir, A. Basit, M.R.A. Bhatti, G. Abbas, Polylactic acid/lyocell fibre as an eco-friendly alternative to polyethylene terephthalate/cotton fibre blended yarns and knitted fabrics, *J. Text. Inst.* 111 (1) (2020) 129–138.
- [5] M. Fabijański, J. Garbarski, Biodegradable Polymers Poly lactide – Processing, Mechanical Properties. *Polish Tech Rev.* 1 (3) (2023) 11–15.
- [6] K. Oksman, M. Skrifvars, J.F. Selin, Natural fibres as reinforcement in polylactic acid (PLA) composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 63 (9) (2003) 1317–1324.
- [7] T. Mukherjee, N. Kao, PLA based Biopolymer Reinforced with Natural Fibre: a Review, *J. Polym. Environ.* 19 (3) (2011) 714–725.
- [8] M. Murariu, P. Dubois, PLA composites: from production to properties, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 107 (2016) 17–46.
- [9] J. Wang, J. Bai, H. Hua, B. Tang, W. Bai, X. Wang, Characterization and Scalable production of Industrial Hemp Fiber Filled PLA bio-composites, *J. Nat. Fibers* 19 (16) (2022) 13426–13437.
- [10] B. Tawiah, B. Yu, S. Ullah, et al., Flame retardant poly(Lactic acid) biocomposites reinforced by recycled wool fibers - thermal and mechanical properties, *Express Polym Lett* 13 (8) (2019) 697–712.
- [11] S. Jose, P.S. Shanumon, V. Kadam, M. Tom, S. Thomas, Preparation, characterisation and application of biodegradable coarse wool-poly(lactic acid) sandwich composite, *Polym. Bull.* 81 (11) (2024) 10293–10310.
- [12] H.Y. Cheung, K.T. Lau, Y.F. Pow, Y.Q. Zhao, D. Hui, Biodegradation of a silkworm silk/PLA composite, *Compos. Part B Eng.* 41 (3) (2010) 223–228.
- [13] M. Mansourieh, S. Farshbaf Taghinezhad, A. Abbasi, Y. Chen, D. Devine, A Study on the Degradability and Mechanical–Rheological Correlations of PLA/Silk Composites, *J Compos Sci.* 8 (10) (2024) 428.
- [14] O.S. Akintayo, J.L. Olajide, O.T. Betiku, et al., Poly(Lactic acid)-silkworm silk fibre/fibroin bio-composites: a review of their processing, properties, and nascent applications, *Express Polym Lett* 14 (10) (2020) 924–951.
- [15] S. Siengchin, Editorial corner - a personal view potential use of 'green' composites in automotive applications, *Express Polym Lett* 11 (8) (2017) 600.
- [16] V. Naik, M. Kumar, V. Kaup, A Review on Natural Fiber Composite Materials in Automotive applications, *Eng. Sci.* 18 (2022) 1–10.
- [17] L. Jiao-Wang, J.A. Loya, C. Santiuste, On the Numerical Modeling of Flax/PLA Bumper Beams, *Materials (basel).* 15 (16) (2022) 5480.
- [18] Sheikh Md Fadzullah SH, Ramli SNN, Mustafá Z, Razali AS, Sivakumar D, Ismail I. Low velocity impact behaviour of pineapple leaf fibre reinforced polylactic acid biocomposites. *J Adv Manuf Technol.* 2020;14(1).
- [19] Singh KK, Shinde M. Impact Behavior of Fibre Reinforced Laminates: Fundamentals of Low Velocity Impact and Related Literature on FRP. Singapore: Springer Singapore; 2022. doi:10.1007/978-981-16-9439-4.
- [20] S. Gholizadeh, A Review of Impact Behaviour in Composite Materials, *Int J Mech Prod Eng.* 7 (3) (2019) 35–46.
- [21] E. Jalón, T. Hoang, A. Rubio-López, C. Santiuste, Analysis of low-velocity impact on flax/PLA composites using a strain rate sensitive model, *Compos. Struct.* 202 (2018) 511–517.
- [22] J.O. Hallquist, LS-DYNA Keyword User's Manual, Vol. I and II, Livermore Software Technology Corporation (2020).
- [23] D. Gay, Composite Materials: Design and applications, 4th Edition, CRC Press, 2022.
- [24] F. Martínez-Hergueta, A. Ridruejo, C. González, J. Llorca, Deformation and energy dissipation mechanisms of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics: a multiscale experimental analysis, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 64–65 (2015) 120–131.